

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation Report (Acceptance Note) for **TEBT-2024-0014**

Submission information table

Submission Title	ToxRTool use in peer-reviewed literature: a meta-epidemiological study protocol
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0014
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	3 (handling editor + 2 peer-reviewers)
Submission Type	Method (Protocol for Planned Study) ▾
Preprint DOI	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13689866
Evaluation Round	Round 5 ▾
Evaluation Stage	Peer-Review ▾
Evaluation Date	25 Sept 2025
Recommendation	Accept ▾

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript presents the protocol for a study of the appropriateness of the use of ToxRTool in the critical appraisal of toxicology studies. Misunderstanding of how such tools ought to be

applied is a common and important problem in chemical assessment, while empirical data about how appraisal tools are being used by study evaluators is limited. In peer-review, the reviewers found the planned methods to in general be rigorous but asked for further detail on what data is going to be collected to fulfil some of the study goals and recommended some restructuring of the manuscript to make it easier to follow the planned methods.

I am satisfied that the authors have implemented all the recommendations, significantly improving the clarity of the manuscript and presenting a comprehensive protocol for the planned work, and have therefore accepted the manuscript for publication.

Acceptance Note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 4 rounds of revision in response to 2 rounds of editorial triage and 2 rounds of peer-review.

In the editor's opinion, this protocol is a [Category 1 preregistration](#), as some of the data the study will generate necessarily had to be viewed by the authors in developing the protocol, but that data has not yet been analysed by the authors.

According to our Registered Reports policy, the manuscript following from this protocol will be accepted so long as the researchers reasonably adhere to their planned methods.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13787669>